

3-Arylisocoumarin: Synthesis of 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-isocoumarin

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Anisole has been condensed with homophthallic acid in the presence of polyphosphoric acid to furnish 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-isocoumarin. Treatment with alkali, opened the lactone ring giving 4-methoxy-(2'-carboxyphenyl) acetophenone. This was reduced to the dihydroisocoumarin using sodium borohydride. Dihydroisocoumarin on treatment with N-bromosuccinimide gave 4-bromo-derivative which on dehydrobromination with triethylamine yielded the original isocoumarin.

An efficient route described recently for the preparation of isocoumarins without any substituent at position-3 has been described^{1,2}. Buu Hoi *et al*³ devised a general method for the synthesis of 3-arylisocoumarins. They condensed homophthallic acids (or anhydrides) with appropriate phenols in the presence of stannic chloride to obtain 3-arylisocoumarins. Polyphosphoric acid proved to be a better condensing reagent as the products obtained were easier to purify. It is surmised that a keto acid is first formed which undergoes enolisation followed by cyclisation to produce isocoumarin. The present synthesis is an extension of this method to phenolic ether.

was transformed into dihydroisocoumarin (V). Adopting the procedure of Srivastava and Choudhury⁵, IV on treatment with N-bromosuccinimide yielded 4-bromocompound (VI). Dehydrobromination in refluxing triethylamine afforded the original isocoumarin (III). A solution of III in ethanol when refluxed with ammonia produced the isocarbostryl (VII). Alternatively, hydrogenation over Palladium carbon could also afford V.

Experimental

3-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-isocoumarin: A mixture of 2-carboxyphenyl acetic acid (1.80 g), anisole (1.98 g)

Anisole (II) was condensed with homophthallic acid (I) in the presence of polyphosphoric acid to furnish 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-isocoumarin (III) in 50% yield. III on treatment with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide gave the keto acid (IV), which on reduction with sodium borohydride in alkali followed by acidification

and commercial polyphosphoric acid (8 g) was taken in a hard glass test tube and heated at 140° for 1 hr. in a glycerol bath. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and left overnight, and the precipitate was filtered out. The crude product was suspended in aqueous sodium carbonate solution and allowed

to stand for some time. It was then filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave unreacted 2-carboxyphenyl acetic acid. The residual solid was dried, dissolved in benzene and passed through a column of alumina, and recrystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether to afford isocoumarin, (1.2 g), m.p. 121°–22° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 122°). ν_{max}^{KBr} 1740, 1640, 1610, 1520 cm^{-1} , $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 255, 300, 320 nm. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 4.69%. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$: C, 76.18; H, 4.76%).

A solution of the (0.2 g) in ethanol (5 ml) was refluxed with liquor ammonia (10 ml) for 2 hrs. On distilling off most of the ethanol, the isocoumarin separated as a solid mass and was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 241°, (0.18 g). ν_{max}^{KBr} 3420, 1650, 1600, 1520, 1290 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 243, 247, 305 nm. (Found: C, 76.38; H, 5.05; N, 5.49%. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{13}NO_2$: C, 76.44; H, 5.17; N, 5.57%).

4-Methoxy- ω -(2'-carboxyphenyl) acetophenone: A solution of 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-isocoumarin (0.5 g) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed with 20% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (25 ml.). Ethanol was removed on steam bath, the reaction mixture was cooled, acidified with ice cooled hydrochloric acid. The solid separated, was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethyl acetate to afford colourless crystals, m.p. 170°–71° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 171). ν_{max}^{KBr} 1680, 1600, 1510, 1450, 1400 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 270 nm. (Found: C, 71.1; H, 5.45%. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$: C, 71.11; H, 5.55%). 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative of the above was prepared in the usual way. Crystallised product melted at 177°–78°.

Recyclisation of the above keto acid (0.5 g) was effected by heating under reflux with hydrochloric acid for 1 hr. On cooling the reaction mixture, a colourless solid (0.4 g) separated. On recrystallisation from ethylacetate-petroleum ether, the product melted at 121°. The m.p. of the sample on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared earlier remained undepressed.

3-(4'-Methoxy phenyl)-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin:

(A) 4-Methoxy- ω -(2'-carboxyphenyl) acetophenone (0.3 g) in ethanol (5 ml) and dil. Sodium hydroxide solution (3 ml, 10%) was treated with sodium borohydride (0.15 g) in small portions. After the completion of addition, the reaction mixture was kept overnight and then acidified with hydrochloric acid.

The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethylacetate (0.15 g), m.p. 91°–92°.

(B) 3-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-isocoumarin (0.5 g) was dissolved in ethanol (8 ml), shaken with Pd/C and hydrogen gas at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. This process was continued for 1 hr. After removal of the catalyst the solution was concentrated, a solid separated and was recrystallised with ethanol (0.2 g), m.p. 90°–91°. The m.p. of the sample on admixture with an authentic specimen of dihydroisocoumarin prepared by the method (A) remained undepressed. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 5.46%. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$: C, 75.59; H, 5.51%).

Conversion of 3-(4'-Methoxyphenyl) 3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin into 3-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-isocoumarin:

A mixture of the above dihydroisocoumarin (0.2 g), NBS (0.15 g) in carbon tetrachloride (10 ml), close to an illuminated 60 watt lamp, was refluxed. An intense yellow colour appeared initially which faded gradually. After refluxing the reaction mixture for 4 hrs., it was cooled. Succinimide was removed by filtration, and filtrate washed with sodium carbonate solution, followed by water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On evaporation of solvent, a solid was left which on recrystallisation from ethylacetate-petroleum ether furnished the 4-bromoderivative (0.19 g) in colourless irregular prisms, m.p. 135°–36°. (Found: C, 57.7; H, 3.95; Br, 24.1%. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{13}O_3Br$: C, 57.6; H, 3.9; Br, 24.05%).

The above compound (0.15 g) in triethylamine (10 ml) was refluxed for 15 hr. and the solid residue left after the evaporation of triethylamine was triturated repeatedly with ice-cooled (2*N*)-hydrochloric acid, followed by water. Repeated crystallisation afforded the isocoumarin (0.10 g), m.p. 120°–21°.

The compound was identified by direct comparison (mixed melting point; I.R. and U.V.) with an authentic sample prepared earlier.

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